
EFFECT OF QUESTION-ANSWER RELATIONSHIP TEACHING STRATEGY ON PUPILS READING COMPREHENSION ACHIEVEMENT IN OBI LOCAL GOVERNMENT EDUCATION AUTHORITY OF NASARAWA STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of question-answer relationship teaching strategy on pupils reading comprehension achievement in Obi Local Government Education Authority of Nasarawa State. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi-experimental pre-test, Post-test non-randomised control group research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 3,439 primary five pupils made up of 1,318 males and 2,121 females in 2023/2024 academic session in Obi Local Government Area of Nasarawa state. The sample size for the study was 187 primary five pupils drawn using purposive and simple random sampling techniques through multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument utilized for data collection was Reading Comprehension Achievement Test (RCAT). The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts, two in the Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education and an expert in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The content validation was established using the table of specifications. The reliability of RCAT was determined using Kuder-Richardson formular 20 (k-R20) which yielded 0.86. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that pupils taught reading comprehension with question-answer relationship strategy had higher achievement score than those taught using conventional teaching method. Further result showed that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that English teachers should use question-answer relationship strategy in teaching reading comprehension to improve the academic achievement of male and female pupils in primary schools.

Keywords: Question-Answer Relationship, Teaching Strategy, Reading Comprehension Achievement, Conventional Teaching Method, Gender

Introduction

Education is an instrument for acquisition of skills, knowledge and inculcation of habits and values in learners. It also brings about intellectual and attitudinal change that reshapes the human potentials for social, political and economic empowerment. Ogundele, Sambo and Bwoi (2016) asserted that education builds the character of the learners, to get them informed about what is worthwhile, socially acceptable and desirable in their immediate environment and society. Formal education is divided into three levels namely; primary, secondary and tertiary education. This study focused on primary education which inculcates literacy and numeracy skills to enable learners function effectively and contribute to the improvement of the society.

Primary education is an important component of formal education system. Individuals must first pass through primary level of education before proceeding to other levels. The primary education is the foundation upon which all other levels of education are built. Edwin-Ezeoka and Obidike (2023) opined that primary school is the first formal learning institution that exposes pupils to fundamental literacy, numeracy skills and knowledge. In primary school English Language is a core subject in all classes.

English Language is compulsory and core subject that every primary school pupil in Nigeria is expected to pass. According to Gboyega and Abdullahi (2015), English Language is a core curriculum subject and is characterized with phonological, morphological, syntactic and discourse levels. Continuing, Gboyega and Abdullahi asserted that the discourse aspect of English Language centred on the medium through which literacy writing is composed. The teaching of English language in primary school enables pupils to develop the ability to read and communicate effectively. For those who can pursue further education, their success also depends on their communicative proficiency in English as the language of education and learning in the various disciplines (Udosen, 2013). However, Zulya, Nurweni and Putrawan (2013) pointed out that at school, there are many problems faced in learning English, one of which is in answering some questions related to reading comprehension.

Reading comprehension is decoding a message or information in a narrative text. Reading comprehension means not just reading a sentence words to words but understanding the information in a text. According to Diajeng (2017), reading comprehension is a useful act for language understanding and acquisition. Diajeng added that reading comprehension can enlarge student's vocabulary knowledge and upgrade spelling and punctuation. It is the act of understanding the messages that the author of text conveys. Reading comprehension is one of the basic skills that are taught to primary school pupils in Nigeria. The purpose of learning comprehension is to enhance learners' ability to comprehend information from a narrative text. Reading comprehension means making sense of what you read and connecting the ideas in the text to what you already know. Auliatisny and Yasin (2017) defined reading comprehension as a classroom activity that aims to search and to understand the contents of a narrative text. In the context of this study, reading comprehension is the process in which learners understand the meaning of text through the combination of information in the text, prior knowledge and previous experience.

Reading comprehension of narrative text is one of the basic competencies required by pupils. But in reality, the competence of learners in reading comprehension of narrative text is still low (Diajeng, 2017). Similar to this, Nurhayati and Abdul (2019) maintained that reading comprehension is a common difficulty faced by students who read a text, unable to take a meaningful message from what they read about. Yusuf (2015) observed that in some

English classes, the announcement of a reading comprehension lesson or period elicits murmuring and grumbling from pupils as they envision the long time it will require the laborious task of looking for meanings of words in the dictionary. Yusuf (2016) added that what makes matters worse is that after all the time and efforts; pupils fail to comprehend the text which could adversely affect their academic achievement.

Academic achievement has been conceptualized in varying ways by different scholars. Ikwuka and Samuel (2017), defined academic achievement as the outcome of education which indicate the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals and this is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment. Academic achievement indicates the knowledge acquired by learners. Baidoo-Anu (2018) defined academic achievement as grades awarded to individuals at the end of an academic study which are important indicators of ability. In the context of this study, academic achievement is learning outcome of pupils which is determined through class tests and examination.

The persistent poor academic achievement in English Language has been a source of worry to researchers, parents and education stakeholders in primary schools in Obi LGA of Nasarawa State. To buttress this, Yusuf (2015) observed that pupils' academic achievement in English Language in primary schools in North Central including Nasarawa State was very poor as they failed to obtain grades at credit level and above due to difficulty in answering of reading comprehension questions in National Common Entrance Examination. Obi Local Government Education Authority (2023) indicated that the number of candidates that sat for National Common Entrance examinations in the Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) in primary schools for the year 2020, 2021 and 2022 were 18,145, 20,213 and 21,332 respectively and the number of candidates that obtained credit and above in English Language were 9,183, 10,004 and 10,312 which represented 50.6%, 49.5% and 48.3% of the population that sat for the examinations. This shows that there is a decline in academic achievement of pupils in English Language in Obi LGEA, Nasarawa State. The problem encountered by male and female pupils in reading comprehension in Obi LGEA, Nasarawa State may contribute to the decline in academic achievement of pupils in English Language. Many primary school pupils in Obi LGEA of Nasarawa State tend to waste too much time to answer comprehension questions during English Language examinations. The experience of the researcher revealed that during examination, some primary school pupils in Obi LGEA tend to read all the text to answer one question only and then read over the text again to answer the next questions. As a result of this repetition in reading texts several times to answer questions, many pupils run out of time and fail to perform well in the examination. Many factors could influence the achievement of pupils in reading comprehension among them is teaching strategies.

Teachers' teaching strategies are believed to be one of the main factors that contribute to failure of pupils in reading comprehension (Nurhayati and Abdul, 2019). Nurhayati and Abdul added that teachers commonly ask learners to read individually, read aloud and translate sentences one by one. Diajeng (2017) further said that one of the factors behind the failure of the students reading comprehension of narrative text is ineffectiveness of conventional teaching strategies used by teachers

The conventional teaching technique is a teaching method in which the teacher has total control of the learning environment. In this method, the teacher transmits knowledge to a group of passive learners. Mashur (2015) posited that the conventional teaching technique in the process of teaching and learning focuses on how the teacher delivers information rather

than how the students absorb it. Continuing, Mashur (2015) averred that it tends to involve more passive learning by the learners, such as listening to the teacher disseminate the information and it is up to the learners to absorb and process it. This is an indication that the technique has its weaknesses with regard to its effectiveness in increasing pupils' reading comprehension ability. Teachers' application of appropriate innovative teaching method in teaching reading comprehension of narrative text could enhance pupils' understanding of the passage.

There are a lot of teaching strategies that could be used by teachers to stimulate pupils' motivation and interest in reading comprehension. Diajeng (2017) noted that the application of appropriate teaching strategies will attract learners to be active in teaching reading comprehension of narrative text. Mashur (2015) asserted that to help learners understand reading comprehension, it is essential for teachers to use an interesting teaching technique to present their teaching materials which is expected not only to increase student's ability in reading but also to help them in creating fun in the classroom. Nguyen and Nguyen (2018) pointed out that one of the strategies is the Question-Answer Relationship Strategy (QARS) which could help pupils track down information with a view of comprehending and then answering reading questions.

Question-answer relationship strategy has been described in a variety of ways by different scholars. Roosantie (2014) defined Question-Answer Relationship (QAR) strategy as an instructional activity designed to help pupils work with a standard feature of reading, answering questions based on a text. It gives the knowledge of where answers can be found in a passage. Nguyen and Nguyen (2018) defined QAR as a strategy to clarify students' approaches in framing reading strategies by understanding question types to comprehend texts. It provides a framework for comprehension of instruction and answering questions. QAR strategy guide pupils to understand text and answer question from it. According to Mashur (2015), QAR strategy is one of the techniques in teaching reading which comes up with the answers to solve the problems by presenting ideas for learners to reason. QAR strategy enables learners to categorize comprehension question based on where to get information in the text to answer question. In this research, QAR strategy is a teaching technique in which teachers guide pupils on the nature of reading comprehension questions, how and where to find the answers.

QAR strategy can encourage and stimulate pupils in answering text questions. Auliatishny and Yasin (2017) pointed out that QAR strategy could arouse the interest and confidence of learners in answering comprehension question. It could enable pupils to understand the nature of question types in a passage. Utami, Salija and Sultan (2023) maintained that QAR strategy can help the learners to search for any information about the text to make them understand it whether it is provided literally in the text or even more advanced than that.

There are many forms of QAR strategy. According to Raphael cited in Nguyen and Nguyen (2018), the QAR strategy consists of four question types including 'Right there', 'Think and search', 'Author and me', and 'On my own.' Raphael cited in Nguyen and Nguyen added that 'Right there' questions are text-explicit questions and the answers of 'Right there' questions are found at one place in the reading texts. 'Think and search' questions are text-explicit questions but the answers of 'Think and search' questions are synthesized in the information from the different parts in the texts. 'Author and me' questions are text-implicit questions and the answers of 'Author and me' questions are found by

relating the information in the texts to readers' prior knowledge. 'On my own' enables pupils to use their prior knowledge in answering comprehension text irrespective of their gender.

Gender is the physical and biological feature that distinguishes male and female. According to Onyali and Nnebedum (2018), gender is a physical, biological and behavioural characteristics which differentiate masculinity and femininity. Gender differences in pupils' academic in reading comprehension have been examined for some time resulting in substantial empirical studies. Yadollah, Afsar and Manouchehr (2015) asserted that differences in the learner's gender identity often lead to differences in intellectual activities including reading. Continuing, Yadollah asserted that the characteristics associated with being male or female provide a better predictor of the learner's reading skill or motivation to read. On the other hand, Pagal, Mirafuentes and Ypanto (2017) argued that females are much capable to read, comprehend and write compared to males. Furthermore, Pagal et al (2017) observed that there is a statistical difference between learners' gender and reading comprehension achievement. On the contrary, Koban-Koç (2016) observed that there was no statistically significant difference between males and females achievement in reading comprehension. Although, these controversial findings might be probably because the studies were carried out with different locations and utilized different classes and reading comprehension content which were tested under varying experimental conditions. The need arose for new studies to take gender into consideration in an attempt to build new evidence on effect of question-answer relationship teaching strategy on primary school pupils reading comprehension achievement in Obi local government area of Nasarawa State.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent decline of 50.6%, 49.5% and 48.3% in academic achievement of pupils in English Language in National Common Entrance Examination for the years 2020, 2021 and 2022 have been a source of worry to researchers, parents, education stakeholders and even the pupils themselves. It appears that primary school pupils in Obi LGA find it difficult to answer questions from reading comprehension. During examination, some primary school pupils in Obi LGA tend to read comprehension text several times but fail to comprehend the text. This worrisome situation may be attributed to conventional teaching method that appears to be applied by most primary school teachers in Obi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. Conventional method of teaching limits the room for learners' active participation in the instructional process, seldom takes into account individual differences makes pupils uninterested in class, discourages learning and creates boredomness.

Primary school pupils are of different gender enrolled in either public or private schools located in rural and urban areas which could affect their reading comprehension achievement. The gender is associated with different roles and expectations that could determine the reading comprehension achievement of pupils. The use of question-answer relationship in teaching reading comprehension is one of the innovative instructional delivery strategies through which students' interest in a subject could be stimulated. In the light of the above, the problem of the study was to find out the effect of question-answer relationship teaching strategy on primary school pupils reading comprehension achievement in Obi LGEA of Nasarawa State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to ascertain the effect of question-answer relationship teaching strategy on pupils reading comprehension achievement in Obi Local Government Education Authority of Nasarawa state. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method.
2. Mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy.
3. Mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy?
3. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method.

Methods

Quasi-experimental research design was adopted in this study. Nworgu (2015) defined quasi-experimental research design as an experiment where random assignments of subjects to experimental and control groups are not possible. This research design is appropriate to this study because it allowed the researcher to manipulate variables under carefully controlled conditions so that the effects of these manipulations could be observed without random assignments of subjects to experimental and control groups. Specifically, it involved pre-test post-test as pre-test was used to eliminate the initial group differences in the sampled subjects and create a base line from which the effect of the treatment would be determined. The study was carried out in Obi Local Government Area of Nasarawa state. Nasarawa state is located in North-central zone of Nigeria. The choice of Obi education local government authority as the area of the study is informed by the current high level of commitment of the people to education through allocation funds to the sector for training primary school teachers on the application of question-answer relationship to enhance understanding of reading comprehension.

The population of the study comprised 3,439 primary five pupils made up of 1,318 males and 2,121 females in in Obi Local Government Education Authority of Nasarawa State. The sample size for the study was 187 primary five pupils drawn using multi-stage sampling procedures. In the first stage, purposive sampling technique was used to sample four primary schools that meet the criteria for the study on the basis of gender composition, qualified teachers and good learning environment. In the second stage, simple random

sampling (balloting without replacement) was used to draw four intact primary five classes into control and experimental group. In the third stage, simple random sampling technique without replacement was used to select two schools for the experimental group and the other two for the control group. The sample size for the study was 187 respondents made of 88 pupils for experimental group (39 males and 49 females) and 99 pupils for control group (44 males and 55 females).

The instrument for data collection was Reading Comprehension Achievement Test (RCAT). The instrument was adapted by the researcher from First School Leaving Certificate standardized tests of 2016, 2017 and 2018. The instrument was divided into two sections. Section A elicited information on the gender of the pupils, while section B is made up of 15 multiple objective test items with four different answer options. The topic covered only reading comprehension in the primary five syllabuses. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation. The content validation was established using table of specification. The face validation was determined by three experts, two in the Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education, and an expert in in the Department of Science Education, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The suggestions were applied in producing the final instrument used for the study. The reliability of the instrument was established using Kuder-Richard 20 which yielded a reliability of 0.86. The coefficient value was adjudged high enough for the instrument usability. This is in line with Shrestha (2021) who advocated that coefficient value of 0.70 or above is adequate for establishing the reliability of research instrument.

The research assistants who are English Language teachers in primary five classes from the sampled schools in Obi LGA were briefed for two weeks regarding the teaching methods. The experimental group teachers were given detailed explanations on how to incorporate the question-answer relationship strategy into the lesson and the general requirements of the research. The study lasted for six weeks using the normal period allocated for English Language in the sampled schools.

Randomization is one of the procedures used to control initial group difference in non-experimental studies. In order to avoid experimental bias in the study, the regular English Language teachers in the two schools under the study was briefed as research assistants and used. Pre-test sensitization was controlled in this study through a longer time interval of five weeks between the pre-test and post-test. To minimize the effect on pupils in the two groups growing older, improve in achievement which could affect the outcome of the study, the researcher limited the experimental period to six weeks. To control this internal validity threat, the items in the instrument was renumbered and reshuffled to minimize the ability of the pupils realizing that they were being re-tested.

Data obtained were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In the test of hypotheses using ANCOVA, F ratio value was used to determine the acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses. The null hypothesis was rejected if p-value is less than the level of significance (0.05), if p-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, null hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method?

Table 1: Mean Pre-test and Posttest Achievement Scores of Pupils taught Reading Comprehension using Question-Answer Relationship Strategy and those taught using Conventional Teaching Method

Method	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Pretest SD	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
QARS	88	3.36	10.17	0.96	1.94	6.81
CTM	99	2.99	6.43	0.92	1.36	3.44

Table 1 shows that pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy had pre-test achievement mean score of 3.36 with standard deviation of 0.96, while their posttest mean achievement score was 10.17 with 1.94 value of standard deviation and mean gain of 6.81. Those pupils that were taught reading comprehension with conventional method had pre-test achievement mean score of 2.99 with standard deviation of 0.92, while their posttest mean achievement score was 6.43 with 1.36 value of standard deviation and 3.44 mean gain.

The mean achievement gain difference between pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method was 3.37 in favour of the experimental group. The spread of score in the posttest is more homogenous among pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method because the SD scores is smaller (1.36) compared to the SD score (1.94) of those taught using question-answer relationship strategy. The result indicated that pupils taught reading comprehension with question-answer relationship strategy had higher achievement score than those taught using conventional teaching method.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Table 2: Summary of ANCOVA on Difference between the Mean Achievement Scores of Pupils taught Reading Comprehension using Question-Answer Relationship Strategy and those taught using Conventional Teaching Method

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	797.338 ^a	2	398.669	201.674	.000	
Intercept	416.529	1	416.529	210.709	.000	
Pretest	147.035	1	147.035	74.380	.000	
Method	512.316	1	512.316	259.165	.000	S
Error	363.731	184	1.977			
Total	13712.000	187				
Corrected Total	1161.070	186				

a. R Square = .687 (Adjusted R Square = .683)

Table 2 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 186 df denominator, the calculated F is 259.165 with P-value of .000 which is less than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy

Table 3: Mean Pre-test and Posttest Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Pupils taught Reading Comprehension using Question Answer-Relationship Strategy

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Pretest SD	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
Male	39	3.51	10.10	1.10	2.01	6.59
Female	49	3.24	10.22	0.83	1.90	6.98

As shown in table 3, the pretest mean achievement scores of male pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy was 3.51 with standard deviation of 1.10, while their posttest mean achievement score was 10.10 with 2.01 value of standard deviation and mean gain of 6.59. Female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy had pre-test achievement mean score of 3.24 with standard deviation of 0.83, while their posttest mean achievement score was 10.22 with 1.90 value of standard deviation and 6.98 mean gain.

The mean interest gain difference between male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy was 0.39 in favour of the females. The spread of score in the posttest is more homogenous among female pupils because the SD scores is smaller (1.90) compared to the SD score (2.01) of males. The result indicated that female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy had higher mean achievement score than their male counterparts.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA on Difference between the Mean Scores of Achievement Scores of Male and Female Pupils taught Reading Comprehension using Question Answer-Relationship Strategy

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	86.179 ^a	2	43.089	15.118	.000	
Intercept	281.653	1	281.653	98.820	.000	
Pretest	85.856	1	85.856	30.123	.000	
Gender	3.434	1	3.434	1.205	.275	NS
Error	242.264	85	2.850			
Total	9431.000	88				
Corrected Total	328.443	87				

b. R Square = .262 (Adjusted R Square = .245)

Table 4 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 87 df denominator, the calculated F is 1.205 with P-value of .275 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy.

Research Question 3: What are the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method?

Table 5: Mean Pre-test and Posttest Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Pupils taught Reading Comprehension using Conventional Teaching Method

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Pretest SD	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
Male	44	2.82	5.93	1.04	1.47	3.11
Female	55	3.13	6.84	0.79	1.13	3.71

Table 5 indicated that the pretest mean achievement scores of male pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method was 2.82 with standard deviation of 1.04, while their posttest mean achievement score was 5.93 with 1.47 value of standard deviation and mean gain of 3.11. Female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method had pre-test achievement mean score of 3.13 with standard deviation of 0.79, while their posttest mean interest score was 6.84 with 1.13 value of standard deviation and 3.71 mean gain.

The mean interest gain difference between male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method was 0.6 in favour of the females. The spread of score in the posttest is more homogenous among female pupils because the SD scores is smaller (1.13) compared to the SD score (1.47) of males. The result indicated that female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method had higher mean achievement score than their male counterparts.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method.

Table 6: Summary of ANCOVA on Difference between the Mean Scores of Achievement Scores of Male and Female Pupils taught Reading Comprehension using Conventional Teaching Method

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	74.995 ^a	2	37.498	33.540	.000	
Intercept	128.887	1	128.887	115.284	.000	
Pretest	54.995	1	54.995	49.190	.000	
Gender	10.016	1	10.016	8.959	.004	S
Error	107.328	96	1.118			
Total	4281.000	99				
Corrected Total	182.323	98				

c. R Square = .411 (Adjusted R Square = .399)

Table 6 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 98 df denominator, the calculated F is 8.959 with P-value of .004 which is less than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that pupils taught reading comprehension with question-answer relationship strategy had higher achievement score than those taught using conventional teaching method. This agreed with the finding of Auliatisny and Yasin (2017) which showed that students who are taught using QAR strategy get better reading comprehension than the students who are taught by using conventional strategy. This also supported the finding of Tiya and Zulfitri, (2023) which revealed that question-and-answer relationship strategy has higher effect on students' reading comprehension achievement than conventional teaching method. The positive effect that QAR strategy has over conventional teaching method on pupils' reading achievement could be attributed to the fact that it offers pupils the opportunity to learn that the answers to some questions are "Right There" in the text, that some answers require a reader to "Think and Search," and that some answers can only be answered "On My Own,". QAR strategy enables pupils to recognize that they must first consider the nature of questions in a reading passage before developing answers to them.

Pupils taught using QAR can actively engage in the construction of meaning within text by becoming aware that answers can be found in the text and some required gathering information from several parts of the text relating it to their own experience and putting together to make meaning. This successful involvement of pupils in reading passage requires the use of prior knowledge, thinking and reasoning which is enhanced through QAR strategy.

It was found that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using question-answer relationship strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method. This affirmed the finding of Ernaini (2018) which showed that there was a significant difference of the students' reading achievement after being taught through QAR strategy and conventional teaching method. This is in consonance with the finding of Meita, Zelvia and Riswanto (2020) which indicated that there was significant difference in students reading comprehension achievement between the experimental group taught using QAR strategy and control group taught using conventional teaching method. The reason for the significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pupils taught reading comprehension using QAR strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method could be the interactive learning environment created by QAR strategy to improve the understanding and retention of comprehensive passage presented to pupils.

The result of this study showed that female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy had higher mean achievement score than their male counterparts. This is in disagreement with the finding of Utami, Salija and Sultan (2023) which showed that mean achievement score of male students in reading comprehension increased higher than their female counterparts after using QAR strategy in the reading class. The possible reason for this finding could be attributed to the different pattern of behaviour, attitude and expectation of male and female pupils. Male pupils may probably prefer to get involved in more social and sports activities compared to their female counterparts which could prefer to engage in reading to improve their reading comprehension achievement mean score when taught with QAR strategy.

Further the result indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy. This refuted the finding of Utami, Salija and Sultan (2023) which indicated that male and female students differ significantly in their reading mean achievement score after exposure to QAR strategy. QAR strategy gives equal learning opportunity to both male and female pupils which could explain the finding of no significant difference in their mean achievement scores.

It was found that female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method had higher mean achievement score than their male counterparts. This affirmed the finding of Anene, Adinna and Ifejiolor (2021) which indicated that the mean achievement of female students exposed to conventional teaching approach is greater than that of their male counterparts. This agreement in findings could be explained by the fact that the studies were conducted in the same country where conventional method is dominantly used in teaching reading comprehension. The finding could be explained by the fact conventional teaching method involve teacher doing the talking on certain subject matter and the students learning female students could prefer to learn by listening than their male counterparts which prefer action. Conventional teaching method probably takes into account the special learning needs of females than males in reading comprehension. The female pupils have tendency to sit calmly and listen to the teacher than their male pupils in the

classroom setting where conventional teaching method is used which could account for high reading achievement than their male counterparts.

It was also indicated that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught reading comprehension using conventional teaching method. This is contrary to the finding of Kenni (2020) who reported that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught with conventional teaching method. The studies were conducted in the same country which could explain the agreement in the findings. Conventional teaching method does not have the features that appeal differently to male and female pupils differently which could account for the finding.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that question-answer relationship strategy is an effective technique of teaching reading comprehension in primary schools in Obi LGA, Nasarawa State. Question-answer relationship strategy is more effective and superior than conventional method of teaching reading comprehension in primary schools. The teachers' use of question-answer relationship strategy in teaching reading comprehension has significant effects on the reading comprehension achievement of male and female pupils in public and private primary schools located in rural and urban areas. However, female pupils taught reading comprehension using question answer-relationship strategy and conventional teaching method had higher mean achievement score than their male counterparts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. English teachers should use question-answer relationship strategy in teaching reading comprehension to improve the academic achievement of male and female pupils in primary schools.
2. National Commission for Colleges of Education should incorporate QAR strategy in their curriculum so that prospective primary teachers will be acquainted with the basic skills of making use of it in reading comprehension.

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